

ADOPTION OF GREEN FINANCE AND GREEN INNOVATION FOR ACHIEVING CIRCULARITY: AN EXPLORATORY REVIEW AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Kshitij Bansal

Department Leader, Procter & Gamble, India.

ABSTRACT

“Green finance (GF) and green innovation (GI)” emerged as the pivotal enablers for addressing the global sustainability challenges, fostering transition from the linear economic models to the circular economies. Together, they are forming backbone of a circular economy, a model underscoring regenerative processes, resource efficiency and waste reduction. This exploratory review is synthesizing the existing research to investigate the integration of green innovation and finance in achieving the circularity. Using the approach of systematic literature review, the study identifies the critical themes, gaps in existing literature and theoretical underpinnings. Key theories like “the Stakeholder Theory and Resource-Based View (RBV)” are explored to understand institutional drivers the green practices. The findings underscore the need for a collaborative ecosystem for involve the financial institutions, policymakers, and corporations to scale this form of practices. Furthermore, the paper also explores how the innovative financial mechanisms, regulatory frameworks and technological advancements are interconnected for promote sustainability.

Keywords: Green finance, green innovation, circular economy, sustainability, resource efficiency, Stakeholder Theory, Resource-Based View, financial mechanism

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1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainability has become the focal point in business strategy and global policy discussion due to environmental challenges like “biodiversity loss”, “resource depletion” and “climate change”. In the context of green GI and GF, they are generally recognised as the essential driver of the transition towards a “circular economy (CE)”. CE is the paradigm shift from the traditional model of “take-make-dispose” to prioritise the regenerative system, reduce waste, and improve resource efficiency. The introduction analyses the convergence of green innovation, green finance and circularity for adaptation. Green finance encompasses the financial instruments like climate funds, sustainable loans and green bonds, to mobilise capital to promote the project which is beneficial for the environment. At the same time, Green Innovation influences the implementation, diffusion and creation of eco-friendly practices and technology which minimises environmental influences. These two domains are linked without innovations, without financial support and innovation cannot achieve the scale, finance may not generate the desired environmental returns.

Figure 1: Investment gap in “sustainable development goals (SDG) sector” from 2023 to 2030

(Source: Dyvik, 2020)

In the case of potential synergies adaptation of GF and GI faces challenges like fragmented financial ecosystems, lack of standardisation and regulatory inconsistency which hinder the effectiveness of green finance. Barriers like high R&D costs, insufficient collaboration with stakeholders, and limited market adaptation obstruct green innovation. Addressing this barrier needs an integrated approach which combines a robust instructional framework. The concept of circularity helps enhance integration, circularity emphasises the designing of the waste out of the system to maintain material and products at a higher value and regenerate the natural system. “Difficulties in accessing to financing resources can impede investments in green technology” (Yu et al. 2021). However, achieving circularity needs a systematic change across the industries of the policy framework and supply chains. “An

estimated 3.8 trillion U.S. dollars is missing to reach the sustainable development goals in developing countries by 2030” (Dyvik, E. H., 2020). Promoting sustainable strategies for effectively balancing environmental innovation and financial constraints helps to leverage the potential to practice for creating value for the business.

Research Aim

The research aims to analyse the integration of green innovation and green finance as the key drivers for achieving circularity in the economic system.

Research Objective

- To access to the relationship between GI and GF for promoting sustainable practices in the circular economy
- To analyse the challenges and barriers faced by policymakers and businesses in adopting the practices of GF and GI.
- To explore the technological, financial, and regulatory enablers this can facilitate the transition towards a CE by green finance and innovation.

Research question

- What is the relationship between green GI and GF for promoting sustainable practices in the circular economy?
- What are the challenges and barriers faced by policymakers and businesses in adopting the practices of GF and GI?
- Who are the technological, financial, and regulatory enablers which can facilitate the transition towards a circular economy by green finance and innovation?

2. METHODOLOGY

This research engages a “systematic literature review methodology (SLR)” to analyse the adoption of green innovation and green finance in achieving the circularity. The SLR approach helps to ensure a replicable, comprehensive, scientific, transparent or unbiased analysis of an existing body of knowledge. SLR helps in collect the data related to the publications and documents which get fit in a pre-defined inclusion criteria for answer the research question (Mengist, Soromessa &Legese, 2020). The databases of Science Direct, Springer, Scopus, Web of Science, ResearchGate, Sage Pub and mdpi are chosen for reviewing the search articles of investigating field. They have a large database of citations and abstracts of the peer-reviewed articles globally, which contain articles of relevant publishers. Before finding articles in the investment field, first the keywords are selected to search research articles. Some of the search strings that are used to explore the research articles are:

String 1: Green Finance, Green innovation, technology, innovation, sustainable or green technology innovation

String 2: Circular economy finance, social innovation and circularity, financing, eco-innovation or climate finance

From the developed search string, the use of options of advanced search string in databases. A three-step process was used to identify relevant literature. For addressing the stages of exclusion and inclusion criteria, the articles published in peer-reviewed journals from 2020 to 2024, focusing on “sustainability, circular economy, green finance and green innovation” are included. The non-English publication is excluded, databases like ScienceDirect, Scopus, Web of Science, and etc were searched using keywords like “green finance,” “green innovation,” “circular economy,” and “sustainability”. First, an initial database search is yielded near about 100 articles. Then, second, a title and abstract screening helped to narrow the scope to 50

articles. Then, finally, a full-text review refined the selection of 25 articles which also met the criteria of inclusion. The exclusion and inclusion criteria of the retrieved literature contribute to adding quality to the assessment criteria for retrieved the literature (Van Dinter, Tekinerdogan & Catal, 2021). These articles are mainly categorised based on the thematic relevance of circularity, green finance and green innovation.

Figure 2: Steps taken for performing systematic literature review

(Source: Self-developed)

3. SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

Table 1: Systematic literature review

SL. No.	Year of publication	Author	Research Title	Methodology	Findings	Total citations
1.	2022	Zhou, Zhu & Luo	“The impact of fintech innovation on green growth in China: Mediating effect of green finance.”	Provincial panel data from 2011 to 2018 are taken for conducting a quantitative data analysis.	“The impact of fintech on the green growth innovation helps to reflected how the dynamic of fintech innovation are also focuses on promoting the GF development of by using some mechanisms like green credits”. The level of technology innovation and financial science may promote growth of green economic.	411
2.	2022	Akomea-Frimpong et al.	“A review of studies on green finance of banks, research gaps and future directions.”	The qualitative data was gathered through the systematic review methodology, to analyse the existing studies on the green finance in the banking sector context.	The finding of the study revealed “there are seven prominent GF products of banks such as green investment, green loan/bonds, green infrastructural bonds, climate finance, carbon finance, green insurance and green securities”.	385
3.	2021	Chen & Chen	“Can green finance development reduce carbon emissions? Empirical evidence from 30 Chinese provinces”	Both qualitative and quantitative data for data collection are used in this research for the data analysis process.	The finding of the study states that “the GF development, because of effect of the spatial spillover, and an inhibit form of carbon emissions growth within the local regions, and it allows to reduces the adjacent regions' carbon emissions dynamic”.	184

4.	2024	Sadiq et al.	“The impact of green finance, eco-innovation, renewable energy and carbon taxes on CO2 emissions in BRICS countries: Evidence from CS ARDL estimation.”	A primary quantitative method for data collection is employed.	The results showed that “eco-innovation, green financial, industrialisation and carbon taxes are negatively linked with emissions of CO2”.	52
5.	2022	Tan & Zhu	“The effect of ESG rating events on corporate green innovation in China: The mediating role of financial constraints and managers' environmental awareness.”	The research employed a primary quantitative method for data collection through “an unpack quasi-natural experiment based on the 2015 ESG rating of the SynTao Green Finance Agency.”	The results show that the “rating of ESG ratings is significantly promotes the quality and quantity of a corporate GI and it also get mediated through alleviating the increasing financial constraints and managers' environmental awareness”.	374
6.	2024	Kumar et al.	“Green finance in circular economy: a literature review.”	This study employed a systematic literature review through analysis of the secondary data.	The finding of the study states that “GF has potential to help the society, provide sustainability, and give prevention to shifts in the climate, by investing to circular economy”.	52
7.	2021	Xu, Liu & Shang	“R&D investment, ESG performance and green innovation performance: evidence from China.”	The study employed the quantitative data collection process through analysing 223 Chinese companies between 2015–2018	The findings of the study focuses that the investment in R&D has positively impacted the performance of ESG and GI which can increase patents of GI. “In addition, the ESG performance moderates the relations of green innovation performance and R&D investment”.	237

8.	2021	Muganyi, Yan & Sun	“Green finance, fintech and environmental protection: Evidence from China.”	A primary quantitative method for data collection is employed in this research	The study explores that “fintech development are generally contributes to reduced industrial gas emission and augments the initiatives of investment towards environmental protection dynamic”.	470
9.	2022	Rasouline zhad & Taghizad eh-Hesary.	“Role of green finance in improving energy efficiency and renewable energy development.”	This study Employed the “stochastic impact through a regression on population, affluence, and technology (STIRPAT) model”.	The findings state that the green bond is the suitable process to promote green energy project and significantly reduce the emission of CO2, there is also no causal linkage between this short-term variable.	437
10.	2023	Ning et al.	“Green bond as a new determinant of sustainable green financing, energy efficiency investment, and economic growth: a global perspective.”	The primary quantitative method is employed in this study through conducting the survey.	The finding of the study revealed that the bank loan has become the main source of financing for the project in relation to energy efficiency. However green banks are invested in private and public funds dynamic for energy efficiency to promote the economic growth.	174

Table 2: Important words used in the research articles and their number of occurrences

Words	Occurrence
Green finance	40
Green innovation	67
Circular economy	112

Supply chain	31
Stakeholder	17
Economic growth	14
Sustainability	20

3.1 Cluster 1: Green innovation and finance

Fundamental to any form of sustainable or green growth strategy is known as green innovation. The study by (Tolliver et al. 2021), provides the backdrop for green innovation importance, as an optimal path towards sustainable development includes to equipping economies dynamic with the growth-driving and pollution-free industries. GI and GF are the practices of financial techniques for incentivise and support environmentally friendly technological advancement which is also important to district the capital for business and projects which reduce the environmental influences and sustainable practices like clean transportation, energy efficiency and renewable energy through using the tools like green investing, green loan and green bonds. The concept of green innovation incorporates with the technological improvement which enables the recycling of waste, prevents pollution and saves energy and it also can include corporate environmental management and green product design. Green financing allows to inclusion of the financial flow level from not-for-profit, private and public sectors for prioritise of suitable development.

3.2 Cluster 2: Green finance and sustainable development goals (SDG)

Green financing is promoted by the changes in the regulatory forms, an increase of green financing for different sectors and harmonising the incentives of public financial dynamics within the SDG environmental dimensions. It also helps in increasing the financing for more a “sustainable”, “natural” and “resource-based green economies”, the green economy of climate and investment towards green and clean technologies for increased use of green bonds. The key areas for current work of green finance are the capacity for building community enterprises on the micro-dimensional areas, promoting partnership at the public-private partnership of green bonds and support of the public sector for creating an enabling environment. The investors use the SDG sector as a benchmark for influence and they also create demanding sustainability bonds (Lee, 2020). The bond market has seen the appearance of another label that proliferating in the loan market, like the “environmental, social, and governance (ESG)” performance of incentive loans.

3.3 Cluster 3: The growth of renewable energy and GE

Renewable energy growth helps to increases the expenditure of energy and promotes affordable and green energy. GF plays a key role in the growth of renewable energy through providing resources and capital needed to reduce the footprint of carbon and expand the dynamic of renewable energy infrastructure. “The total global energy transition investment towards decarbonisation amounted to 1.78 trillion U.S. dollars in 2023, which was a new record (Fernández, 2024).” The transformative shift for sustainable development plays a major role in GF for catalysing the growth of renewable energy sectors.

Figure 3: Global energy transition investment 2004-2023

(Source: Fernández, 2024)

The global community grappling with the challenges of change in climate for integrating the financial mechanism for supporting environmental sustainability become vital (Chen, Umair & Hu, 2024). Green finance encompasses the green bond; carbon market and invention in the renewable energy are emerging as cornerstones in the pursuit of sustainable economic growth and ecological resilience. The transition towards the source of renewable energy is important through investigating the mechanism of GF and efficiency for promoting solutions of sustainable energy. Renewable energy stocks have outperformed fossil fuel stocks for some decades, mainly for any long-term investment, hold and buy investors can foster difference in the changing environmental dynamic. The investment in renewable energy mainly refers to the allocation of financial resources in technologies, companies and projects which generate the power from the sources of renewable energy.

4. RELATED INSTITUTIONAL THEORIES

4.1 “Resource-Based View (RBV) theory”

RBV theory poses that the firm capabilities and resources are the key drivers of the competitive advantage which makes it highly relevant in the GI and GF context for achieving circularity. RBV is based on the link between the internal resources of the firm and strategy (Valaei et al. 2022). As per RBV, the firms which possess non-substitutable, valuable, rare and inimitable resources can create towards the sustained competitive advantages. In the case of green innovation and green finance, these resources can include the financial capital, an advanced technological capabilities, human capital and intellectual property. RBV is useful to understand the dynamic through which the firms leverage these resources to scale and develop green innovations.

From the perspective of green finance, the RBV sheds light on how the firms are utilise the financial resources, like “ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) investments or green bonds”, to fund sustainability initiatives and green innovations. The ability to secure the financial resources are depends on firms to demonstrate the capability to deliver more focused on sustainable goals, which need to access to the skilled human resources and cutting-edge

technologies. RBV uses “sustainable” typically for the strategic management through linking “sustained” to its competitive advantage (Freeman, Dmytriyev & Phillips, 2021). RBV emphasises that GI and GF are intertwined with the firm internal resources and capabilities, suggesting that the practices of sustainability offer the firm a long-term competitive edge in the increasingly co-conscious markets.

4.2 “Stakeholder Theory”

Stakeholder theory (ST), states that organisations have to consider the interests of every stakeholder, not only shareholders, in the processes of decision-making. This theory is relevant to GV and GI due to its sustainability efforts need the engagement of diverse stakeholders, such as investors, communities, consumers, NGOs, and governments. ST is utilised for the analysis of stakeholders, as a key method for stakeholder management which examines and recognises the stakeholders to determine the best practices for the organisation to get engaged (Mahajan et al, 2023). For green finance, the ST emphasises the role of an investor who is increasingly looking to align its portfolios for sustainability goals.

Sustainable funds, ESG investment and green bonds are all financial instruments which reflect the interest of stakeholders concerned with environmental outcomes. Stakeholder theory is “corporate responsibility” as opposed to “corporate social responsibility”, and an organisation demonstrates responsibility through its actions and decisions concerning their stakeholders (Barney & Harrison, 2020). Companies which get engage with the initiatives of green finance are addressing its immediate financial goals and consumers demand a greater transparency on environmental impact.

5. DISCUSSION

The adoption of GF and GI has gained a momentum in recently, which was driven by the growing urgency to address global environmental challenges and need of sustainable economic growth. Both are critical for advancing circularity dynamic, an economic model that focuses to regenerating the whole natural systems, increasing efficacy of resource and reducing waste. Financial institutions utilise the green bonds to supplement loans or funds, not necessarily for funding the green resources in exact location (Abbas et al. 2023). In 2014, the worth of green bonds is “37 billion U.S.”, and it gets to its peak in 2021 with approximately “594 billion U.S. dollars” (Statista Research Department, 2024). While there is a slightly decreased in 2022 and 2023, when the green bonds issued the3 amounted to “510 billion and 588 billion U.S. dollars”. While Lamperti et al. (2021), state that, under the large climate risks threat, policies of green financial are used to supplement the “standard climate policy tools” to put economy on a sustainable growth path of zero-emission. The systemic integration of GF and GI plays a critical role in facilitating transition of circular economy.

Figure 4: Green bonds value issued globally between 2014 and 2023

(Source: Statista Research Department, 2024)

Financial mechanisms like sustainable investments and green bonds give some necessary capital to fund the projects which enhance the resource efficiency and reduce the environmental harm. Green economy shift is from a growing economy which needs an obligation through country leadership dynamic which focuses to provide dimension of green financing (Khan et al. 2022). Chin et al. (2024) mention that green finance is the key driver of sustainable development and environmental protection. Green finance providing funding and it is also directing the financial resources toward the projects which get align with the environmental sustainability goals. Innovations in sustainable product design, renewable energy and recycling technologies are examples of technological advancements that can drive the objectives of the circular economy. These innovations help to allow an efficient resource use and materials regeneration, which further help in minimising the waste and reducing the need for virgin resources. While ESG investments and green bonds are growing, there is a lack of universally accepted metrics which help in measuring the environmental impact of investments.

Table 3: Comparison between the related theories

Theories	Main-focus	Key-factors	GI and GF Relevance	Challenges in adopting GI and GF
RBV theory	Competitive advantages within sustainable practices	Resource, fund sustainability initiatives and green innovations	Long-term sustainability and competitive advantage, particularly as	Difficulty in analysing the key resources, the funds-related

			consumers and investors	initiatives like an adaptation of sustainable practices of the supply chain, designed for long-term use and reuse of resources.
Stakeholder Theory	Public awareness of environmental issues rises	Green bonds, ESG investments and sustainable funds	The diffusion and development of green technologies need collaborative efforts across the value chain.	As the public awareness of environmental issues rises, services which align with its values and consumers are increasingly seeking products. Companies which fail to meet the expectations of environmental-conscious stakeholders risk losing reputational damage and market share.

Table 4: GI Technologies and GF: the Future Dynamic and Challenges

Clusters	Challenges	Proposed research questions (PRQs)
“Green innovation and finance”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GI and GF face poor incentives and regulatory gaps for the local firms to adopt the ambitious climate goals. 	PRQ1: Does green growth through innovation allow for environmentally adjusted multifactor productivity?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Issues like difficulties in accessing to the financing sources which result in an inadequate explanation of the expectations of investors. 	<p>PRQ2: What is the influence of Green Finance Performance and Mechanisms on different green finance tools?</p> <p>PRQ3: what are the policies behind the green economic growth?</p>
<p>“Green finance and sustainable development goals (SDG)”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financing for the climate crisis and SDGs is compromised through the pressing competing requests and priorities. • After the COVID-10 pandemic situation, different countries are facing crises like fiscal deficiency and debt crises. 	<p>PRQ1: What are the challenges faced by green finance for different countries?</p> <p>PRQ2: What are the influences of the recent trends in GF?</p> <p>PRQ3: What role can GF play in the sustainable development?</p>
<p>“Green finance and renewable energy growth”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renewable energy fencing dynamics face challenges in the current market dynamics like high capital costs, lack of the adequate debt financing and short tenure of loans. • Low investment return and lack of a long-term financing are the key challenges to diffusion of the renewable energies. 	<p>PRQ1: How have green bonds attracted the attention of the policymakers and industrial sector?</p> <p>PRQ2: What are the influences of green bond financing on social and environmental sustainability?</p> <p>PRQ3: How do the financial products contribute to achieving the goals set out for the use of renewable energy resources?</p>

6. IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study offers different implications for policymakers, researchers and practitioners, emphasising the importance of GI and GF in the broader framework of the circular economy. For policymakers, the study emphasises the need for clear regulatory frameworks which incentivise sustainable practices. Policymakers should enforce and establish regulations which support mechanisms of GF like sustainable tax incentives, carbon pricing and green bonds. Green finance provides some potential opportunities for the businesses to expand and grow, which is also restricted due to the environmental control (Jahanger et al. 2024). The government should prioritise R&D investment for foster environments and green technologies which encourage private-public partnerships. Through doing so, they reduce the financial risk

associated with green innovation and encourage a wider adaptation of sustainable practices. For business, the research underscores the importance of aligning its strategy with sustainability goals both to meet the regulatory requirements to appeal to a growing base of environmentally-conscious consumers.

7. CONCLUSION

Green finance comprises instruments like “carbon trading mechanisms”, “sustainability-linked loans” and “green bonds” that mobilise capital for projects which deliver the environmental benefits. Green innovation focuses on the diffusion and development of eco-friendly business models, technologies and processes. Achieving the systemic change needs a multifaceted approach which integrates technological innovation and financial mechanisms, represented by GI and GF. However, transitioning the circular systems needs technological transformation and substantial investment, emphasising interdependence of innovation and finance. The study allows discourse on the sustainability and gives an actionable insight for the stakeholders who aim to integrate the green practices into the economic systems. Consumer demand for sustainable products is the key driver of green innovation, as the businesses recognise the economic benefits of aligning the strategies with shifting the public attitudes to environmental responsibility.

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